

Evaluating the effect of feedstock and electrodes' pretreatments on bioelectrochemically improved anaerobic digestion process

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Introduction

- An enhanced biogas and biomethane production can be achieved by integrating AD with bioelectrochemical systems (BES)
- This synergistic approach holds promise for accelerating biogas production kinetics within AD systems and converting part of its biogenic, residual CO₂ content into additional methane¹
- Promoting the availability of biodegradable matter in feedstocks² and promoting biofilm adherence on carbon fibre brushes³ are key factors impacting AD-BES efficiency
- Various pre-treatments (PT) were proposed for lignocellulosic feedstocks, such as ultrasound, thermal, sieving and grinding
- Carbon fiber brushes are adopted as electrodes for AD-BES. Due to their hydrophobic nature, thermal pretreatment (BES Th-PT) was proposed to enhance biofilm adhesion

Figure 1. AD-BES reactor

Material and methods

Agroindustrial feedstock pretreatments

■ Grease ■ Agri-food effluent ■ Fruit-vegetable waste ■ Sludge ■ Middlings/bran ■ Silage ■ Straw ■ Bovine manure ■ Poultry manure ■ Liquid manure

Figure 2. Experimental campaign 1

Figure 3. Experimental campaign 2

Electrode pretreatments

Overnight acetone soaking + 450°C 30 min

AD-BES operation

- Replicate, single-chamber AD-BES of 1L, vs CTRL AD without electrodes
- Three-electrode system: WE and CE = carbon fiber brushes; RE = Ag/AgCl electrode
- Reactors were continuously mixed and heated at 35°C, adopting an HRT of 10 days
- The inoculation was done with the same digestate used as feedstock
- AD-BES operation at 0,3 V

Results

Feedstock PT effect on digestate characteristics

Parameter	Energy-intensive		Mechanical	
	Ultrasound	Thermal	Sieving	Grinded
BOD ₅ (g/L)	+66%	+63%	-18%	+279%
Cond. (mS/cm)	+5%	+4%	-21%	+11%
Viscosity (Pa s)	-94%	-65%	-54%	-6%

Feedstock PT effect on biofilms bioelectrochemistry (CVs)

Figure 4. Anode and cathode CV of AD-BES (note the different Y-scale)

Electrode PT effect on biofilms bioelectrochemistry (CVs)

Figure 6. Anode and cathode CV of AD-BES (note the different Y-scale)

Electrode PT effect on AD-BES

Figure 7. CH₄ production rate of AD-BES and current density

Feedstock PT effect on AD-BES

Figure 5. CH₄ production rate and yield of AD-BES vs CTRL (dimension-less values), and current density

- Methane production rate for AD unit was 0,10 L/L_{react}/day, and methane production yield was 16 L/kg COD
- Si PT increased methane production yield of AD-BES
- US PT applied to digestate increased the methane production rate and yield of AD-BES vs CTRL

Conclusions

- Digestates PT increase electrical conductivity and decrease viscosity (important parameters for AD-BES)
- Biodegradability is significantly improved by US and Th PT of the digestate by more than 60%
- US enhances methane production yield and rate in AD-BES
- Combination of substrate PT and an optimal voltage improved AD-BES performance and internal resistance in terms of current density
- AD-BES Th reactor increased its current density and biogas quality compared to AD-BES

1. C. Reddy et al., *Chemosphere*, **287**, 132299 (2022).
 2. M. R. Atelge et al., *Fuel*, **270**, 117494 (2020).
 3. Y. Feng, et al., *Journal of Power Sources*, **195**, 1841–1844 (2010).

